

PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIPS AND PARENTING STYLES WITHIN THE FAMILY

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Annotatsiya: Bilamizki, Ota-onalar bilan bola o'rtasidagi munosabatlar oilaning asosiy va markaziy qismi hisoblanadi. Bu munosabatlarning sifatli bo'lishi, bola shaxsiyatining rivojlanishiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Oila tarbiyasi esa, bola hayotidagi dastlabki ta'sirchan muhitni yaratadi. UShbu maqolada esa Oilada ota onalarning munosabatlari va tarbiya uslublari, shu bilan birgalikda, ularning farzandlarining kelajakdagi ta'siri haqida yoritilgan.

Аннотация: Мы знаем, что отношения между родителями и ребенком являются основной и центральной частью семьи. Именно качество отношений оказывает большое влияние на развитие личности ребенка. С другой стороны, семейное воспитание создает раннюю аффективную атмосферу в жизни ребенка. Однако в этой статье рассказывается об отношениях и стилях воспитания родителей в семье, а также о будущем влиянии их детей.

Abstract: We know that the relationship between parents and a child is the main and central part of the family. It is the quality of the relationship that has a great impact on the development of a child's personality. On the other hand, family education creates an early effective atmosphere in a child's life. However, this article talks about the relationships and parenting styles of parents in the family, as well as the future influence of their children.

Kalit so'zlar: Avtoritar ota-ona uslubi, demokratik ota-ona uslubi, g'amxo'r ota-ona uslubi, haddan tashqari himoya, oilada ota-onaning do'stona uslubi, ota-ona va bola munosabatlari

Ключевые слова: Авторитарный стиль воспитания, Демократический стиль воспитания, Заботливый стиль воспитания, чрезмерная защита, Попустительский стиль воспитания в семье.

Keywords: Authoritarian Parenting Style, Democratic Parenting Style, Caring parenting style, overprotection, Conniving family parenting style.

The parenting style in a family refers to a set of attitudes, concepts, principles, and values that create the conditions for a child's development and preparation for life in society. While the dominant type of parental influence is usually considered, it is also important to take into account who dominates in the family and how they do so, as well as the significance of each family member's impact on the child. However, it is common to see disagreements between parents regarding the same actions of the child, depending on the style of their relationship. In psychology, there are six main types of parenting styles: authoritarian, permissive, democratic, uninvolved, rejecting, and over-protective. Each style has its own unique characteristics and can affect a child's mental health and personal growth in different ways.

There are several different parenting styles in families. Let's take a look at some of them. For example, **Authoritarian Parenting Style**

Under an authoritarian parenting style, parents suppress a child's independence, strictly directing and controlling their actions and decisions. They use physical punishment, coercion, and shouting to discipline for even minor infractions. Parents give orders and instructions, without considering the child's opinion or offering compromise. In these families, obedience and respect for tradition are highly valued,

and rules are not discussed. Parents believe they are always right and disobedience should be punished, often through physical means. Children's independence is limited, as parents do not feel the need to justify their demands or offer explanations. As a result, children are deprived of love, affection, and empathy from their parents, who only care about raising them to be obedient. Parents strictly monitor the homework of younger students, sometimes even standing next to them and putting pressure on them in an attempt to make them act independently. In response, children use various strategies to protect themselves, such as crying or feigning helplessness. This can lead to children losing interest in learning and having difficulty concentrating in class.

Teachers working with these students should be aware that they may have little interest in learning, but they are often eager to receive high grades at any cost. These students may react poorly to criticism and always find someone to blame when things go wrong. They may struggle to make friends, as they are not able to give selflessly or adapt to a group setting. Instead, they tend to want to be the center of attention and may blame others for their own problems. Parents of these students often complain that their children do not enjoy school and are not allowed to express themselves. In reality, these children may ignore or reject the suggestions of their teachers and classmates, harshly criticizing everything that occurs in the classroom without offering any solutions.

Democratic Parenting Style

A democratic parenting style is characterized by warm relationships between parents and children, moderate discipline, and hopes for their future. It also involves frequent communication and caring for children's emotional well-being. Democratic parents create a loving atmosphere in the home and provide emotional support. They are firm and consistent in their expectations, yet fair in their approach. They

encourage personal responsibility and independence in their children according to their age and abilities. This style of parenting differs from conniving parenting, which is often based on manipulation and control.

Parents create discipline by using rational and problem-solving strategies to ensure their children's independence and, if necessary, adherence to group rules. They require their children to conform to established standards of behavior and monitor their compliance. "Family rules are more democratic than authoritarian." Parents use reasonable arguments, discussions, and persuasion instead of force to achieve mutual understanding with their children. They equally listen to their children and express their expectations to them. Children have an alternative: they are encouraged to propose solutions and take responsibility for their actions. As a result, these children believe in themselves and the possibility of fulfilling their responsibilities. When parents respect their children's opinions and values, it benefits both parties.

The impact of a democratic parenting style on a child's personality: According to research, children from democratic families rank first in terms of self-esteem, ability to lead, and faith in their parents' beliefs. They respect authority, are responsible, and control their desires. These children are more confident and responsible, so they are less likely to abuse drugs or alcohol and engage in criminal activity. They also experience fewer phobias, depression, and aggression. The research also shows that these children are less susceptible to negative peer influences and more successful in forming positive relationships with their peers. A democratic parenting style balances control and independence, resulting in competent, responsible, independent, and confident children. These children are more likely to develop high self-esteem and self-confidence, less aggression, and generally achieve greater success in life.

Conniving family parenting style

From a young age, parents give the child complete freedom of action. Adults in these families are often busy with their own lives. They don't pay much attention to the child's mental state, and they are indifferent to their needs and requests. Sometimes they don't even consider it necessary to pay attention.

Parents use inconsistent and clumsy methods of punishment and reward. They can punish a child and then immediately reward him. The main way of education in these families is "carrot and stick". Parents build their relationships with their children in such a way that they inadvertently cultivate the search for beneficial forms of interaction, encouraging the development of qualities such as obedience, flattery, and sycophancy in children.

The influence of a permissive parenting style on children's character: Children from such families often show a lack of interest in mental or physical work. During lessons, they become quickly tired and try to avoid working under any pretext. These students often treat teachers' assignments and responsibilities unfairly, and can be self-confident to the point of being rude.

Surprisingly, children from permissive families often become the most unhappy. They are more likely to experience psychological problems such as depression and phobias. There is also a high likelihood of them engaging in antisocial behavior. Research has shown a connection between permissive upbringing and juvenile delinquency, substance abuse, and early sexual activity. Since children have not been taught how to control their behavior, they are less likely to develop a sense of self-esteem. This lack of discipline leads them to want to establish some form of supervision, so they "put a lot of effort into trying to control their parents and get them to control them."

The influence of an unsupportive parenting style on children's adaptation in society is significant. Unmet psychological needs can lead children to become vulnerable and unable to handle daily challenges, preventing them from fully participating in society. This, in turn, hinders their social development and the formation of positive self-esteem. Without high goals and expectations, children often have difficulty controlling impulses and tend to be immature and unwilling to take responsibility.

As teenagers grow older, they may come into conflict with adults who do not understand their needs, are unable to consider the interests of others, and do not establish strong emotional connections. They may also feel fear and uncertainty about the future, as they are not prepared for the restrictions and responsibilities that come with adulthood. On the other hand, teenagers may perceive the lack of parental guidance as a sign of indifference or emotional rejection. This can lead to feelings of fear and insecurity, as they seek guidance and support from others.

Caring parenting style (overprotection)

The desire to constantly be around the child, solving all the problems that arise for them. Parents closely monitor the child's behavior and limit their independent actions, worrying that something might happen to them. Underlying the mother's desire to "tie" the child to her, not letting go of them, are often feelings of anxiety. The need for constant presence becomes a ritual that reduces anxiety, especially the fear of loneliness or lack of recognition. Therefore, anxious mothers are more likely to be protective.

Effects of overprotective parenting on a child's personality: Despite the external care provided, the overprotective parenting style can lead, on the one hand, to an excessive emphasis on the child's importance, and on the other - to the development

of anxiety, helplessness, and delayed social maturity. The child grows up feeling helpless, insecure, and neurotic, which can lead to difficulties in socializing.

Some adolescents may try to escape from their parents' excessive control and attention, becoming aggressive, disobedient, and self-centered. Constant monitoring and restrictions may also foster a child's ability to become sneaky and cunning over time. In adolescence, children may begin to use lies as a defense mechanism against adults' constant interference in their lives, leading to alienation and distance from parents, which is especially dangerous at that age. A child who is accustomed to excessive care may become obedient and comfortable with their parents. However, this external obedience often masks self-doubt, lack of self-reliance, and fear of making mistakes. The consequence of overprotecting a child can be the development of dependence on others, including negative influences from other people. This can lead to dependence, financial difficulties, infantilism, self-doubt, avoidance of risks, and contradictory personality traits, as well as lack of timely communication skills.

In conclusion, each parenting style has its advantages and disadvantages. The most effective style that meets a child's needs and characteristics is based on democratic principles. Parents need to constantly monitor their child's mental and emotional state, behavior, and development. A mutually respectful relationship between parents and children and the right parenting style help form a balanced and healthy personality.

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